

Summary

We investigate why the strength of the Antarctic Circumpolar Current (ACC, Fig. 1) varies strongly across the current coupled climate models in the control runs and the 21st century scenarios.

Figure 1. The mean circulation in the Southern Ocean. The ACC is depicted in dark blue, confined by two fronts, the Polar Front (to the south) and the Subantarctic Front (to the North, both in dark blue lines). The volume transport of the ACC is 137 +/- 8 Sv (Cunningham et al., 2003). Figure from V. Zlotnicki, JPL.

The variations among the control runs are not easily explained, but it turns out that the “GM” parameterization of the eddy-induced transports has a very strong influence on the ACC.

For the projected changes of the ACC strength in the 21st century, no significant statement can be made. Fyfe and Saenko (2005) had suggested that the – already observed – strengthening and poleward shift of the west wind band might lead to an increased ACC transport in the future. We cannot corroborate this result. Instead, we show that the surface density flux changes tend to decrease the ACC transport.

The CMIP3 models

We compare 25 AOGCMs from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project phase 3 (CMIP3) multi-model dataset that was used for the IPCC AR4. The data used here are the last 20 years of the control runs and the years 2081–2099 of the SRES A1B scenario, from all models that provided the 3D ocean fields.

model	model
1 bccr_bcm2_0	14 ingv_echam4
2 cccma_cgcm3_1_t47	15 inmcm3_0
3 cccma_cgcm3_1_t63	16 ipst_cm4
4 cnrm_cm3	17 miroc3_2_hires
5 csiro_mk3_0	18 miroc3_2_medres
6 csiro_mk3_5	19 miub_echo_g
7 gfdl_cm2_0	20 mpi_echam5
8 gfdl_cm2_1	21 mri_cgcm2_3_2a
9 giss_aom	22 ncar_ccsm3_0
10 giss_eh_2	23 ncar_pcm1
11 giss_model_e_h	24 ukmo_hadcm3
12 giss_model_e_r	25 ukmo_hadgem1
13 iap_fgoals1_0_g	26 observed

Table 1. Model numbers used on this poster (except for Fig. 4). The GFDL and MPI data were partly obtained separately.

Control runs

There is a considerable spread of the ACC strengths across the AR4 models (Fig. 2). There is no simple explanation for that as the correlations with e.g. wind stress (Fig. 2) or density gradients are not strong (Russell et al., 2006).

Figure 2. ACC strength (volume transports across Drake Passage at 69°W) from the control runs versus (a) maximum zonally averaged wind stress and (b) the position of this maximum. Model numbers see Table 1. Horizontal model resolution plays no role. Model 4 however stands out with a shallow ridge in the Drake Passage area (max. depth 1100 m).

ACC change in the end of the 21st century

We compared the ACC strength in the models’ control runs with the projected change in the end of the 21st century in the SRES A1B scenario (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. ACC strength (averaged, in Sv) in the control run (x-axis) and the change towards the end of the 21st century SRES A1B scenario (y-axis). Model numbers: see Table 1

The mean ACC across the models is 146 +/- 72 Sv in the control run and 142 +/- 68 Sv in the SRES A1B scenario. The drop in the mean value is not significant. In observations from the period 1993–2000 no change can be detected (Cunningham et al., 2003).

Across the CMIP3 models the relative change of the ACC varies from -18% to +40%. Changes in wind stress cannot explain this spread as all models show a stronger wind stress over the Southern Ocean. The resulting additional Ekman transports should accelerate the ACC.

It turns out that this tendency is opposed by the changes in surface density fluxes that reduce the meridional density gradient in almost all models (Wang, Kuhlbrodt and Meredith, submitted; Fig. 4).

(c) Southern–Northern density flux trends

Figure 4. Differential density flux trends over the 21st century. The negative values for almost all models indicate that the areas south of the ACC lose density faster than the areas north of the ACC. This reduces the meridional density gradient and tends to weaken the ACC. Note the different model numbers used here. From Wang et al., submitted.

A growing spatial extent of the subpolar gyres can also reduce the ACC strength.

Eddy-induced transports

Mesoscale eddy activity is strong along the ACC. It restratifies the ocean, as opposed to the Ekman transport that steepens the isopycnals (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Sketch of the meridional overturning in the Southern Ocean. From Marshall and Radko (2003). The eddy-driven overturning ψ^* counteracts the wind-driven overturning $\bar{\psi}$.

In coupled climate models the eddy-induced transports are usually parameterized as an additional isopycnal advection of the tracers (Gent and McWilliams, 1990; “GM”) that is proportional to the slope of the isopycnals. The proportion is given by the thickness diffusivity κ . Often chosen as a constant, it can be diagnosed from the isopycnal slope too (Visbeck et al., 1997).

The influence of the Gent & McWilliams parameter

We defined a GM index for each model. It is 1 if GM is not implemented, 2 if the GM implementation uses a constant κ , and 3 if κ is diagnosed from the stratification. For the GM=2 models we also compared the numerical κ values. The models with the more sophisticated Visbeck-type parameterization show less spread in the ACC strength and also in the projected ACC changes (Figs. 6a,b).

Figure 6. The role of the GM index (a, b) and the value of κ (c, d) in determining the strength of the ACC in the control runs (a, c) and the projected change in the 21st century (b, d). For model numbers see Table 1.

For the models with a constant κ the correlation with the ACC is very good (Fig. 6c). If κ is large then there is a strong tendency to re-stratify. This leads to flat isopycnals and a weak geostrophic transport, and vice versa for a small κ . For the 21st century changes the picture is less clear, however models with a small κ tend to show a weakening (Fig. 6d).

From eddy-resolving model studies it is known that κ can vary by a few orders of magnitude and may well be negative too. The strong dependence of the ACC on one individual parameter shown here suggests to rather use a variable κ . Eventually it is desirable to overcome the GM parameterization and resolve the oceanic eddy-induced transports in coupled climate models.

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Contact me

Till Kuhlbrodt
Department of Meteorology, NCAS-Climate
University of Reading
Earley Gate, Reading RG6 6BB, UK
t.kuhlbrodt@reading.ac.uk phone: +44 118 378 6014